

THE LEXICOGRAPHIC STUDY OF ANTHROPNYMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK
LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This thesis is devoted to the lexicographic study of anthroponomy (personal names) in the English and Uzbek languages. The research analyzes the representation of anthroponomy in dictionaries, their origins, semantic features, and their connection with national and cultural factors. The formation, classification, and lexicographic description of personal names in English and Uzbek are examined from a comparative perspective.*

Key words: *Anthroponomy, lexicographic descriptions, onomastic, English language, Uzbek language, dictionary.*

Introduction. Language is an important means of reflecting a nation's culture, history, and worldview. Among linguistic units, anthroponomy, that is, personal names, hold a special place, as they are closely connected with people's traditions, religious beliefs, historical processes, and social life. Anthroponomy constitute an essential branch of onomastic, and their study is of great theoretical and practical significance in linguistics.

In recent years, the lexicographic study of anthroponomy—namely, their presentation, interpretation, and classification in dictionaries—has become increasingly relevant. In particular, a comparative linguistic analysis of anthroponomy in English and Uzbek helps to reveal the close relationship between language and culture.(12)

Anthroponomy is onomastic units that include personal names, surnames, and nicknames given to individuals. In lexicography, anthroponomy are mainly recorded in special dictionaries or in separate sections of explanatory dictionaries. The lexicographic description of anthroponomy provides valuable information about their etymology, semantic characteristics, and historical development.

In English, anthroponomy are often formed on the basis of the Bible, Greek and Roman mythology, historical figures, and occupational names. For example, names such as John, Michael, and Elizabeth originate from religious sources.(1)

In contrast, Uzbek anthroponomy are largely based on national traditions, religious beliefs, and words expressing positive qualities, such as Dilshod, Baxtiyor, Muhammad, and Zaynab.(2)

English anthroponomy is usually explained in specialized onomastic dictionaries. Such dictionaries provide information about the origin of a name, its original meaning, historical usage, and famous bearers. For instance, works like the Oxford Dictionary of First Names enable a systematic study of English anthroponomy.

In Uzbek, although there are relatively few dictionaries specifically devoted to anthroponomy, information about personal names can be found in certain explanatory and etymological dictionaries. Many Uzbek anthroponyms are borrowed from Arabic, Persian, and Turkic languages, which plays an important role in indicating their origins in lexicographic sources. (3)

A comparative analysis of English and Uzbek anthroponomy shows that personal names in both languages reflect national culture. While individualism and historical heritage are strongly represented in English anthroponomy, Uzbek anthroponomy emphasize positive qualities, religious beliefs, and family values. From a lexicographic perspective, English anthroponomy have been studied through systematic and comprehensive dictionaries, whereas in Uzbek lexicography there remains considerable work to be done in this field. The use of modern lexicographic methods can contribute to a deeper and more detailed study of Uzbek anthroponomy. (6)

Conclusion. In conclusion, the lexicographic study of anthroponomy in English and Uzbek reveals the close relationship between language and culture. Anthroponomy are not only means of personal identification but also important linguistic units that reflect a nation's historical memory and cultural identity. A comparative linguistic and lexicographic analysis of anthroponomy in English and Uzbek can make a significant contribution to the further development of onomastic and lexicography.

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